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COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGIES AND SOCIAL CHANGE: A DEVELOPING NEW PERSPECTIVE

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ABSTRACT

The need to connect, to share, to appreciate and be appreciated, to know, to be liked has always been a want of human nature since times immortal, though Face book molded the expression in an e-way and competition among cellular companies has made technology accessible to every individual. But even the times when technology was not so in-handly there were other things like real friends to play with, books to read, parents who were willing to listen with an open heart and plentiful of time. Though this virtual presence, this texting style, smiley's instead of written expression, these copy pasted googled emotions, this need to be connected 24/7 with the world without even realizing what's happening next room or next door and this self obsession is driving everybody crazy. But then it's high time now to realise the importance of equilibrium thereby not to let ourselves vault into an altogether e-world but focus on some very basic things like- to care, memories to cherish, to empathise, to respect, as nothing in the world can ever replace a warm handshake, a hug and a pleasant smile.

Key Words: Social Change, Communication Technology,

INTRODUCTION:

Communication has always had the power to facilitate social, economic and technological development. It is no longer only the exchange of information by speaking, writing, or using some other medium but rather it has become instant, interactive, expressive and virtually connected.

The world in the recent times is converging into an informative, knowledge based society because of the new information communication technologies. People are changing the way

they communicate. Our work places, our home, cafes, malls and leisure places give the look of, in Toffler's phrase, "The electronic cottages" where people not only work but also study and surf. The explosive growth of the Internet and World Wide Web has brought astonishingly increased attention to the social implications of all kinds of information and communication technologies (ICTs). The urge for communication is changing the boundaries of traditional institutions such as the family, community, firms and universities. Also, traditional practices, ranging from entertainment and shopping to news gathering and learning are also undergoing major changes.

The need to connect, to share, to appreciate, to be known and be liked has always been a want of human nature since times immortal. Further these social networking sites changed the way of expression in an e-way. Also competition among cellular companies has made technology accessible to every individual.

If we have a look around a restaurant we will find people using their cell phones to text, Tweet, or update their Face book status—all while sharing a meal with others at their table. Social media's effect on our way to interact and communicate with the world is visible throughout all areas of society. So what does this mean for interpersonal communication? According to Paul Booth who is an assistant professor of media and cinema studies in the College of Communication at DePaul University in Chicago, social media certainly affects how we engage with one another across all venues and ages. "There has been a drastic shift in the way we communicate; rather than face-to-face interaction, we're trending towards mediated communication," he says. "We'd rather e-mail than meet; we'd rather text than talk on the phone."

According to Booth, studies have shown that people actually are becoming more social and more interactive with others, but the style of that communication has changed so that we're not meeting face-to-face as often as we used to. The impression of distance disappearance is gradually intensifying day by day. The face and makeup of communication is changing as the means of communication today's era are constantly changing, evolving and developing. Face to face communication is gradually and swiftly converging into virtual communication. Social networking sites such as Twitter, Face book, e-mail, texting, on-line transactions, on line shopping sites are just a few examples which are diminishing the verbal communication among people.

The world is changing at a very fast pace. Just a few years back twitter is no more a bird's sound, cloud is not just in the sky, 4G is not any more a parking place. Victor Hugo said, "There is nothing more powerful than an idea whose time has come". And the time has come

where verbal communication has decreased dramatically and has been taken over by technological conversation. Texting first came about in the '90s and has increased dramatically since then and is now used more to communicate rather than calling someone. More than 70 percent of people use their smart phones to text. Normally people carry their phone with them and therefore they don't have to log into a web browser or anything to get on email or social media and also it is far more convenient and accessible.

Face book is also accessed largely through mobile devices, with 751 million users accessing it from a mobile device — more than half of its 1.11 billion users and a 54 percent increase from the mobile users in March 2012, according to Face book. People not only use Face book to communicate, but the great deal of time they spend on it takes away from the time they might spend interacting with people in person. According to dazeinfo.com, 23 percent of users check their accounts at least five times every day. The use of other social media sites, such as Twitter, Pinterest, Instagram and LinkedIn has also skyrocketed, diminishing verbal communication.

More than 163 billion tweets have been sent since Twitter was invented, averaging around 175 million tweets per day in 2012. However, even more time is spent on Instagram than on Twitter. In August 2012, users spent an average of 170 minutes on Twitter via mobile device and approximately 257 minutes on Instagram. More than 5 million photos are uploaded every day, and after two years the app has attracted more than 50 million users, according to dazeinfo.com. Pinterest and LinkedIn have also had their share of visitors, with LinkedIn used primarily for business connections and Pinterest used largely by women. We are living in a globally wired village where the number of internet users is growing every day. Access to information, to exchanges of opinions, emotions, celebrations and what not is the trend now a days. The world is shrinking at a very fast pace because of the technological convergence. We humans have the basic tendency to adapt and change. Thus to conclude one does not need a crystal ball to see that technology has become a part of our life and is no longer a term to foresee. Thus we can say that the average impact of technology convergence in our society is like a facilitator, helper and instructor and also an updated interactive multimedia oriented information service. But also its high time now to realize the importance of equilibrium thereby not to let ourselves vault into an altogether e-world and focus on some very basic things like - to care, memories to cherish, to empathize, to respect as nothing in the world can ever replace a warm handshake, a hug and a pleasant smile.

Objective & Methodology:

The current technological era is diminishing the thin line of age groups but still in context of doing research age has always had its part. Age is one of the important factors of respondents' inclination towards technology oriented devices and thus has been given due place in a study conducted in the Department of Communication management and Technology in Guru Jambheshwar University of Science and Technology, Hisar. In this study from the point of view of age the respondents were divided into three broad categories viz. i) Below 20 years; ii) Between 20-30 years and iii) Above 30 years. The category-wise data of these respondents is given in the following Table:

Age-wise number of respondents

Sr. no .	Age Group	Frequency	%
1.	Below 20 years	73	24.7
2.	Between 20-30 years	85	28.8
3.	Above 30 years	137	46.4
Total		295	100

Source : Interview Schedule

Conclusion :

This study reveals that out of the total 295 respondents 137 (46.4%) falls in the age group of above 30 years while 85 (28.8%) belong to 20-30 years age category and the remaining 73 (24.7%) are in the below 20 years category. From this it can be inferred that the inclination towards technology oriented devices increases with the advancement of age. And this finding can be presumed with the growing availability and inclination of today's generation towards these technology based digital devices. But also this need to connect, to share, to appreciate and be appreciated, to know, to be liked has always been a want of human nature since times immortal, though Face book molded the expression in an e-way and competition among

cellular companies has made technology accessible to every individual. But even the times when technology was not so in-hand there were other things like real friends to play with, books to read, parents who were willing to listen with an open heart and plentiful of time. Though this virtual presence, this texting style, smiley's instead of written expression, these copy pasted googled emotions, this need to be connected 24/7 with the world without even realizing what's happening next room or next door and this self obsession is driving everybody crazy. But then it's high time now to realise the importance of equilibrium thereby not to let ourselves vault into an altogether e-world but focus on some very basic things like- to care, memories to cherish, to empathise, to respect, as nothing in the world can ever replace a warm handshake, a hug and a pleasant smile

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